

Infinity exercise

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A short exercise to quickly clarify the understanding of critical concepts within a group in order to prevent miscommunication. This is especially useful at the start of MA proposal development in order to build a shared language.

Benefits

It supports building a shared understanding and helps in the boundary setting on topics and concepts during proposal design.

Practical recommendations

Preparation

Set up an online whiteboard and identify the critical concept(s).

Round 1 – Introduction (5 min)

Ask each individual to write down 3 words on 3 sticky notes to describe (each) critical concept.

Round 2 – Wining in pairs (5 min)

Put individuals in pairs (e.g., via break out rooms). Each pair needs to agree on the best 3 words. Put these on sticky notes.

Round 3 – Wining in groups of four (5 min)

Put the pairs of the previous round into groups of four. Each group needs to again agree on their top 3 words. Put these on sticky notes.

Round 4 – Reflection (10 min)

Take a look at the final top 3 words from each group of four with the whole group. Are there any key words missing? Take some time to discuss the group's understanding of the critical concept(s) after this exercise.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Working with a diversity of backgrounds

Transparent communication about agendas, expectations and results

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

The infinity exercise method

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